

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth System**

Comparison and validation of two Antarctic SSH products

Deliverable D1.3

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Cover sheet: Schematic of altimetry in the open-ocean and in a sea ice-covered ocean. See Figure 2 for more details. Designed and drawn by Cosme Mosneron Dupin.

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History of Changes

Version	Date	Comment	Authors
Version 1	8 April 2025	Submitted version	Jean-Baptiste Sallée
Version 2	3 March 2026	MDT has been defined, reference to Auger et al. have been corrected. Labels in the colourbars of Figures 7-8 are now legible.	Jean-Baptiste Sallée

1. Publishable summary

Sea Level Anomalies (SLA) are a key parameter of the Earth Climate System. Aside from the societal impact of sea-level rise, measuring SLA allows for the observation of the upper ocean circulation on a large scale (International Altimetry Team, 2021). To do so, we rely on altimetry. With a satellite sending an electromagnetic wave and recording the echo sent back by the surface, also called waveform, most of the ocean SLA field has been monitored over the last 30 years (Cazenave et al., 2014). However, SLA at high latitudes have remained unknown for a long time. This is due to the presence of sea ice, which acts as a physical barrier for altimetry.

Recently, two European groups have developed new satellite-based Sea Level Anomaly (SLA) products, offering unprecedented SLA estimates in the seasonally ice-covered Southern Ocean over the past 20 years. These products have the ability to strongly enhance our understanding of the region's circulation and variability, but have not yet been validated. This deliverable presents the first systematic comparison and evaluation of these products against each other and against independent in situ observations. When compared against each other, both products show consistent SLA estimates with a local mean squared error of 1-2 cm and a correlation above 0.7 in ice-covered regions. The overall error compared to in situ observations is 3-6 cm, reflecting typical uncertainty for these satellite-based products.

2. Work performed and main achievements

2.1 Description of the work performed

2.1.1 Rapid presentation of the two products

Despite its crucial role in global climate dynamics, the circulation of the Southern Ocean remains one of the most mysterious ocean circulation systems on Earth. A major obstacle to understanding this region is the difficulty of observing ocean circulation in areas covered by seasonal sea ice.

In recent years, two groups, both based in Europe (at LOCEAN, France, and at NOC, UK), have been working to produce new satellite-based sea level anomaly (SLA) products focused on the subpolar Southern Ocean, including its sea-ice covered regions. The LOCEAN group produced an estimate of the Southern Ocean SLA from 2002 to 2021 based on four satellite missions: Envisat, Cryosat-2, Sentinel-3A and SARAL/AltiKa. The NOC group made a similar estimate from 2002 to 2018 based on two products, Cryosat-2 and Envisat. Figure 1 shows the time span of each mission.

Fig.1: Overview of the start and end of each satellite mission integrated into the datasets.

Surface echoes, or waveforms, from each mission are analyzed, and the local SLA is extracted from them. Improvement in processing techniques now allows for the retrieval of SLA coming from leads, which are fractures and holes in the sea-ice cover (Peacock et al. 2004). This process is illustrated in Figure 2. The NOC dataset uses a TFMRA algorithm to retrieve the SLA in the leads, while the LOCEAN dataset relies on the ADAPTIVE algorithm described in Poisson et al. 2018.

The approach and the algorithms chosen by the two groups are essentially very different and the two products have been developed completely independently of each other. The comparison presented in this document makes it possible to estimate the uncertainty associated with the data treatment carried out by each group.

Fig. 2: Schematics of altimetry in the open-ocean and in a sea-ice covered ocean. The waveform shapes from both open ocean and leads differ, the leads one being much peakier. Retracking algorithms are now able to extract SLA from both.

2.1.2 Comparison of the French and UK products

The two products are compared and evaluated using a hierarchy of four different approaches of varying complexity:

- A. First, we visually compare time series of SLA from the two products, averaged over large regions of interest (Figure 3-5).
- B. Second, we compute the local root mean square error and local correlation between the two products by comparing time series at each individual grid point (Figure 6).
- C. Third, we visually compare the climatological mean seasonal evolution of the regional pattern of SLA in the two products (Figures 7-8).
- D. Finally, we compare the two altimetry products with fully independent in-situ observations from bottom pressure recorders (BPRs) and tide gauges (Figure 9, Table 1-2).

(A) The two products are first averaged over the entire region south of 30°S (Figure 3). The two resulting time series show excellent agreement both in terms of the size of the anomalies and in terms of variability at all time scales. The largest differences are observed after 2013, where the two products differ in the number of satellites used: the LOCEAN product includes observations from Altika and Sentinel 3, while the NOC product does not (Figure 1).

These conclusions hold for two smaller sectors when the region south of 30°S is divided into a subpolar region (seasonally sea-ice covered) and a region north of the subpolar sector (Figure 4). The LOCEAN product appears to contain slightly larger anomalies in the sea-ice covered region, but mostly the two products give very consistent views of the SLA averaged over these two sectors.

The sea-ice covered regions are then further decomposed into an on-shelf and an off-shelf region (above the Antarctic continental shelf or north of it; Figure 5). Again, we find that the two products are very consistent, even in the very high-latitude continental shelf region, which is affected by sea ice in all seasons.

Fig.3: Globally averaged time series of Sea Level Anomalies for both the (blue) LOCEAN and the (orange) NOC products.

Fig. 4: Globally averaged time series of Sea Level Anomalies for both the (blue) LOCEAN and the (orange) NOC products. Both fields are masked with the Mean Dynamic Topography (MDT) mask in Auger et al. 2022 and averaged. (Top) Global average is done on the data outside of the MDT mask, it corresponds to the ocean never covered by sea-ice. (Middle) Global average is done on the data inside the mask. It corresponds to the ocean partially or constantly covered by sea-ice. (Bottom) The black line encircled the MDT mask, with a bathymetry overlay. The yellow area corresponds to the shelf, i.e. regions with a depth lower than 1000 meters.

Fig.5: Globally averaged time series of Sea Level Anomalies for both the (blue) LOCEAN and the (orange) NOC products. The MDT mask has been applied to both time series. (Top) Sea Level variations off the continental shelf, defined as the region deeper than 1000 metres. (Bottom) Sea Level variations on the continental shelf, defined as the region shallower than 1000 metres.

(B) The previous comparisons are qualitative, but allow a first impression of the differences between the two products by visual inspection. We now want to make a more quantitative comparison of the two products. At each grid point, we calculate the RMSE and the correlation between the two time series from the two products.

The local RMSE between the two products is typically 1-2 cm (Figure 6), smaller than the typical errors expected for this type of product (Auger et al., 2022). Interestingly, the two products are more consistent in the sea ice areas (leads in the histogram of Figure 6) than in the region not affected by sea ice (ocean in the

histogram of Figure 6). This is because the non-ice region is associated with a number of hotspots of very intense SLA variability for physical reasons (ACC, western boundary currents), while the sea-ice region is generally quieter.

The two products show very high local correlations, typically above 0.7, with a peak of the distribution around 0.8 for the seasonally covered sea ice region and 0.9 for the sea ice-free ocean region.

Fig.6: Comparison metrics for both products. (Top) RMSE and correlation between the two products computed for each grid cell time series. (Bottom) Distribution of the RMSE and correlation of each grid cell. The leads (sea-ice covered ocean) and ocean (open ocean) split is done based on the MDT mask.

(C) We continue the comparison by looking at the regional pattern of climatological seasonal SLA anomalies (Figures 7-8). At first sight, the two products reproduce very well similar regional patterns of SLA, both in the subpolar region and north of it. There are some slight differences, especially in the winter months, with slightly larger anomalies on the continental shelf for the NOC product in months 6-9, and a more consistent large-scale pattern in the LOCEAN product in months 8-10. However, the main result is that the two products provide very consistent views of the regional seasonal anomaly patterns.

Fig.7: Side-by-side SLA monthly climatologies, computed on the period 2003-2018. left is LOCEAN product, right is the one from NOC. Figure 7 shows the months from January (month 1) to June (month 6), Figure 8 from July (month 7) to December (month 12).

Fig.8: Same as Figure 7 months from July (month 7) to December (month 12).

(D) All of the previous comparisons give great confidence that the two different and independent data treatments in the LOCEAN and NOC products will give similar results. This is reassuring that the resulting products are not too dependent on ad hoc decisions made during the data treatment. However, the two products are, by construction, highly dependent as they use a similar source of observations before data treatment (Figure 1). The next step is therefore to compare each product with completely independent in-situ observations and gauge their uncertainty. Unfortunately, there is a limited amount of in-situ observations that can be used to validate this type of product. There are two main types of observations that we can use: bottom pressure recorders (BPRs) and tide gauges. Tide gauges provide an almost direct measure of what our SLA product is producing. However, they are often land-locked and may represent local dynamics that are not well captured by the SLA product. BPRs are often deployed further from the coast, but are only affected by baroclinic variability and are therefore most useful for validating SLA variability over a specific frequency band.

We use all available tide gauges and BPRs with data within the period 2002-2018. In total, six tide gauges and six BPRs are used (Figure 9). The correlation of the LOCEAN product with the tide gauges is between 0.4 and 0.75, with RMSE between 3.2 and 5.6 cm. In comparison, the NOC product performs slightly worse but similarly, with correlation = 0.24-0.57 and RMSE = 4.48-5.10 cm (Table 1).

The correlation of the LOCEAN product with the BPR ranges from 0.47-0.85, with an RMSE of 0.74-1.22 cm. In comparison, the NOC product performs similarly with correlation = 0.17-0.86 and RMSE = 0.73-1.69 cm (Table 1).

Fig.9: Comparison of altimetry products with in-situ observations. (Left) In-situ measurements locations, circles are BPRs, stars are tide-gauges. (Middle) Time series comparison for the (blue) SYOWA tide gauge, and corresponding time-series extracted from the (green) NOC and (orange) LOCEAN products. (Right) Time series comparison for the (blue) MyrtleC BPR, and corresponding time-series extracted from the (green) NOC and (orange) LOCEAN products. Rolling average with a window of 100 days has been subtracted for each timeseries, in order to keep the 20-100 days signal.

Tide-gauge	LOCEAN		NOC	
	R	RMSE	R	RMSE
Casey	0.64	3.22	0.29	4.48
Davis	0.59	3.63	0.24	4.92
Dumont D’Urville	0.4	4.82	0.42	4.55
Faraday	0.49	4.4	0.44	4.78
Mawson	0.75	4.04	0.56	4.95
Syowa	0.57	5.61	0.57	5.19

Table 1: Comparison metrics of tide-gauges measurements versus the products SLA. The product time series are obtained by averaging grid cells in a 150 km radius around the tide-gauges locations. Monthly data is used.

	LOCEAN		NOC	
	R	RMSE	R	RMSE
BPR				
DPS	0.47	1.18	0.64	0.97
DPS DEEP	0.63	0.78	0.64	0.86
MYRTLE B	0.48	1.13	0.25	1.39
MYRTLE C	0.77	0.87	0.86	0.73
ANT 17	0.53	1.22	0.63	1.07
JARE	0.85	0.74	0.17	1.69

Table 2: Comparison metrics of BPR measurements versus the products SLA. The product time series are obtained by averaging grid cells in a 150 km radius around the BPR locations. Monthly data is used. The rolling average with a 3 months window is subtracted to keep the variations in the 30-90 days temporal band. Rolling average with a window of 100 days has been subtracted for each time series, in order to keep the 20-100 days signal.

2.1.3 Conclusions

In recent years, two groups, both based in Europe, have worked to produce new satellite-based sea level anomaly (SLA) products that provide unprecedented estimates of SLA in the seasonally ice-covered Southern Ocean region over the past 20 years. These products provide a new perspective on our understanding of the Southern Ocean circulation and its variability, but remain unvalidated. In this paper, we provide the first systematic comparison of these two products, which have followed very different methodological approaches to produce their SLA estimates. We also provide the first systematic evaluation of their performance against independent in situ observations. We show that the two products perform very similarly and produce very consistent estimates of SLA, both when averaged over large regions and when comparing their seasonal-interannual variability, or when comparing their regional pattern of seasonal variability. In the seasonally covered sea ice region, the two products have a local mean squared error of 1-2 cm and a correlation above 0.7. Compared to in situ observations, the LOCEAN product appears to perform slightly better, perhaps because it integrates observations from more satellites than the NOC product. The overall local mean squared error of these products compared to in situ observations is 3-6 cm, which could be considered a typical uncertainty achieved by these two satellite-based products.

2.2 References

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2.3 Open Science

Datasets

The data underlying this deliverable will be deposited on the French Spatial agency Aviso website, as well as on the OCEAN ICE community in Zenodo, with tags pointing to OCEAN ICE. The data will be submitted as soon as the paper describing the dataset and the comparison will be submitted in the coming weeks.

Peer-reviewed publication

A scientific peer-reviewed publication (in open access) describing the French dataset and comparing the French and UK products is in preparation. The authors will select a CC BY licence or equivalent.

3. Results

This deliverable results in the compilation of a new dataset that will be freely distributed to the community and an associated peer-reviewed publication.

4. Impact

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following objectives of the project as described in the description of the action.

O1: Reduce the spatial and knowledge gaps in ocean observations around Antarctica, particularly relating to ice sheet-ocean interaction and deep water formation and export.

This deliverable contributes to this specific objective by quantifying uncertainties and differences between two 20-year sea surface height products in a critical blind spot of the Southern Ocean. The deliverable provides confidence in these products. They reveal 20 years of sea surface height observations in the Southern Ocean ice cover region, greatly reducing the spatial gap in ocean observations, which will allow us to better and unprecedentedly understand the continental shelf ocean circulation and associated interannual-decadal variability.

